

From lab to market: Catalysing research-driven innovations with a novel process model

Authors

Anne-Mari Sandell¹

¹ Forum Virium Helsinki

Abstract

Innovation procurement is often dominated by market demand over research-driven solutions. To truly unlock academia's potential, we need comprehensive and systemic approaches. While agile piloting shows promise, commercialisation requires tailored support and pragmatic methods to accommodate early-stage innovations. Effective innovation ecosystems, accessible Living Labs, and dedicated innovation orchestrators are all crucial enablers. This paper introduces a novel process model for catalysing viable business from academic research, aiming to find sustainable solutions for broader societal problems. Informed by insights from the FinEst Mini-Piloting Programme (2021-2024), this model addresses its successes and shortcomings in fostering collaboration and achieving commercialisation. It is designed to unlock the commercial potential of academic research within agile piloting programmes supported by Living Labs and innovation ecosystems. The model bridges the gap between academic research and successful commercial rollout through a four-phase process: 1) Academic Discovery, 2) Collective Explication, translating research outcomes to match real-world problems via co-creation; 3) Agile Development, iteratively developing and validating solutions in collaboration; 4) Commercial Delivery, featuring a phased rollout. This proposed model and the learnings from the FinEst Mini-Piloting Programme offer a practical contribution to enhancing the commercialisation of research-driven innovations and encouraging academia to harvest the full potential of Living Labs.

Key words

Research-based innovation, Innovation ecosystem, Agile piloting, Living Labs, Innovation procurement

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Addressing the "European paradox" – transforming academic research into market-ready innovations – **enables a significant contribution** to solving wider societal and economic challenges. This paper introduces a four-phase agile piloting process that has been designed to unlock academic research's commercial potential, particularly within agile piloting programmes.

The current market-driven models often fail to unleash academic innovators' full potential; **therefore**, this problem calls for novel approaches. The novel model, developed during the Horizon Europe-funded FinEst Twins project, offers a structured, adaptive pathway for research-based innovations to become **commercially viable** products and services through **agile piloting practices**. The four phases are:

1. **Academic Discovery:** Generates foundational knowledge, together with intellectual property, **forming the basis** for new innovations.
2. **Collective Explication: Co-creation** translates **academic** research into commercially viable solutions that match real-world challenges and end-user needs.
3. **Agile Development:** Living Labs develop research-driven solutions by **employing** an agile piloting approach and iterative validation through continuous feedback loops.
4. **Commercial Delivery:** Focuses on strategic launch and scale-up, informed by agile piloting's iterative feedback, aiming for sustained market adoption.

Living Labs have a **crucial** role in paving the way for successful research-driven innovations by providing authentic, real-life settings for iterative **experimentation** and validation. The principle of co-creation is fundamental, allowing **engagement** of all key stakeholders in active, iterative collaboration that fosters shared ownership. The FinEst Mini-Piloting Programme demonstrated this synergy, showcasing co-creation's power in developing innovative **technologies** that meet the diverse needs of cities and their residents.

The FinEst Mini-Piloting Programme **highlighted** specific challenges for commercialisation of **research-driven** innovations, including significantly longer development timelines. The programme **emphasised** the vital role of skilled orchestrators in **facilitating** the collaboration between innovation ecosystem actors. The proposed four-phase model, empowers academia to translate basic research into solutions for broader societal problems, ensuring sustainable, human-centred urban development.

References

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